

INNOVATION ENVIRONMENT IS THE MOST IMPORTANT CONDITION FOR EFFECTIVE INNOVATION

Shermuhammedov Bekhzodjon Usmonovich

Tashkent Institute of Finance Phd, Associate Professor

e-mail: diplomat_701@Mail.Ru

Komilova Dilafruz Rustamovna

Tashkent State University of Economics

Master's student

e-mail: dilafruz.rustamovna1997@gmail.com

Abstract: This article describes the role of innovative economy and innovative environment in the development of effectively applied innovations. Effective implementation of innovative strategies and projects in the company requires the need for the main components of innovative potential.

Key words: Innovation, innovative environment, strategic goal, business ideas, innovative projects, intellectual resources, innovative potential, national innovative system, personnel potential, infrastructure resources.

Introduction: In recent years, the term "innovation economy" has become popular among both businessmen and scholars. It is the belief that institutions and technological change are the main forces behind economic growth. In recent years, innovation has been seen as a new force of modern capitalism. The term "innovation economy" embraces the idea that entrepreneurs and their new ideas create the "creative destruction that creates new jobs in the future." In other words, entrepreneurship as a process leads to the replacement of existing products or methods with new methods of production.

Main part: Before talking about innovation, it is important to fully understand its nature. In the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, innovation (in English innovations, innovation - introduced innovation, invention): - funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of technology and technology

generations; - it is defined as innovations in the fields of scientific technology, management and labor organization, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity. So, the word "innovation" means "newness" ("novation") and "innovation" (innovation).

The main strategic goal of the development of new Uzbekistan is to restore it as a modern scientific and technological force, based on the production of its scientific knowledge, the use of the results of research and experimental design in the economy for effective commercial purposes. This combination of internal environment and external conditions, defined as the innovation environment, is the main condition for effective innovation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Creating an innovative environment

It is necessary to develop and harmonize the internal and external factors of innovation in order to create the necessary innovation environment that ensures the efficient operation of the innovation process at all stages. The most important condition for the creation and implementation of innovations (business ideas, innovative projects) is the necessary innovative potential of innovative entities, which is characterized as a combination of various resources.

- 1) intellectual resources;
- 2) material (experimental and instrumental base, information equipment);

3) financial;)

4) personnel experience;

5) infrastructure resources, as well as other resources necessary for the implementation of innovative activities. Of course, at the stage of creating an innovative company, entrepreneurs may not have all kinds of resources on the list, but understanding their existence and necessity is also a very important condition for striving to be able to fully implement innovative activities.

Figure 2. Innovation potential - the overall potential of the company as a part of

The existence of innovative potential (as an internal environment of innovation) is a necessary but not sufficient condition for the effective commercialization of the results of scientific and technical activities and the implementation of innovative strategies. As mentioned above, it is necessary to create external conditions suitable for innovative development in order for all links of the innovation process to work effectively and to realize the commercialization of scientific developments. The creation of new institutional structures and changes in the functions of environmental factors are related to its working models, mechanisms of interaction and other institutional structures.

Conclusion: The modern model of innovative development implies the systematic integration of science and technology into the social and economic development of society. Such integration creates strong incentives for the creation

of new knowledge-intensive products and services in the field of science and technology and the formation of a stable flow of effective innovations that allow us to capture traditional markets. As a result, a national innovation system will be formed, which will create new products and services that meet the current demand in terms of quality, price, size and time to market. The successful operation of the national innovation system requires not only strong science and education, but also effective interaction between the public and private sectors as the main "players" in the innovation field. The essence of these systems is to create a public-private innovation partnership in which public and private entrepreneurs act as complementary equal partners. The state supports the scientific and technical sector and the educational system - sources of innovation, provides free access to the results of scientific research in the state sector, creates the necessary conditions for their commercial use, the necessary innovation infrastructure, the system of training qualified personnel and for effective development creates the necessary legal framework.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. A. Taniyev. "Innovative economy". Darslik. - Samarkand, 2020 - 460 p
2. S.R. Topildiev, R.R. Hasanov "Innovative models of social and economic development" Study guide. - Tashkent, 2019 - 206 p.
3. Ayupov R.H., Boltaboeva G.R. Problems and solutions of forming an innovative economy in Uzbekistan.
4. <https://www.valuer.ai/blog/redefining-value-in-the-innovation-economy>